

SECTION OF CHEMICAL SCIENCES

INVESTIGATION OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE CONDUCTIVITY OF CRACKS DURING HYDRAULIC FRACTURING

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Abstract

To increase the efficiency of oil production and productive use of the fund of producing and injection wells, enterprises carry out a large range of works:

- methods of increasing oil recovery (MIOR) of productive formations for extracting residual oil reserves and developing hard-to-recover reserves, the extraction of which is difficult by traditional methods;
- capital and current repairs to maintain the well stock in working condition;
- geological and technical measures (GTM) and processing of bottom-hole zones (BHZ) related to the intensification of oil production and the achievement of optimal production capabilities of wells;
- measures to increase the inter-repair period (MIIP) of well operation based on improving the quality of repair and optimal selection of deep-pumping equipment.

Keywords: cracks during, methods, hydraulic fracturing, pump, oil field, geological and technical measures.

During this complex of works, a significant number of advanced technologies are being developed to affect the formation and the bottom-hole zone, new methods of complex repair and insulation work in wells, new machinery, equipment, tools, and other measures of scientific and technological progress (STP) are being introduced, which increase the efficiency of oil production and the use of wells, increase the productivity of repair teams, reduce the complexity of the operations performed, which ultimately leads to an improvement in the financial situation of oil-producing enterprises. At the same time, the introduction of advanced technologies and new equipment require significant both operational and capital costs and investments.

Hydraulic fracturing is a process in which fluid pressure acts directly on the formation rock up to its destruction and the appearance of a crack [1, 2].

As a result of hydraulic fracturing, the flow rate of producing or pumping wells increases many times due to a decrease in hydraulic resistances in the bottom-hole zone and an increase in the filtration surface of the well, as well as the final oil recovery increases due to the introduction of poorly drained zones and interlayers to the development [3].

The essence of hydraulic fracturing consists in the formation and expansion of cracks in the formation when high pressures are created at the bottom of the well by the liquid injected into the well. Sorted coarse-grained sand or proppant is injected into the formed cracks, the role of which is to prevent the crack from closing after pressure is removed [4]

The purpose of hydraulic fracturing is as follows [3, 4]:

1) increasing the productivity of producing and pumping wells;

2) increasing oil recovery from producing wells, restoring performance characteristics that cannot be restored by traditional methods;

3) the method of development of oil and gas fields.

Scope of hydraulic fracturing [3]:

1) oil fields with complicated development conditions (heterogeneity of formations, low permeability, etc.);

2) producing and injection wells, the productivity of which is lower than potentially possible;

3) injection wells, for changing filtration flows;

4) a wide range of changes and composition of the reservoir in the section, a wide variety of geological structure of the formation;

5) can be used for complex effects on an entire deposit or a section of the deposit.

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A crack is created by pumping liquids of a suitable composition into the formation at a rate exceeding its absorption by the formation. The fluid pressure increases until the internal stresses in the rock are exceeded (Fig. 1)

Figure 1 - Internal stresses in the rock, the rock is torn along the planes of minimum strength

New cracks formed in the formation or existing ones that have opened and expanded, connecting with others, become conductors of oil and gas connecting

the well with the productive zones of the formation remote from the bottom (Fig. 2). The length of cracks into the depth of the formation can reach several hundred meters [5].

Figure 2 - Application of hydraulic fracturing: a - formation before impact; b - formation after hydraulic fracturing. 1 - casing pipe; 2 - borehole; 3 - pumping and compressor pipes; 4 - cracks in the rock formed after hydraulic fracturing

The mechanism of crack formation during rupture can be represented as follows (Figure 1). There are natural microcracks in sedimentary rocks, which are compressed under the influence of mountain pressure. The permeability of such cracks is very small. Under the pressure created by the pumps, the liquid injected into the well is filtered primarily by the zones of greatest permeability, including natural cracks. At the same time, a pressure difference is created between the layers vertically, since in more permeable layers and cracks the pressure will be greater than in poorly permeable or practically impermeable ones. As a result, there is a force acting on the roof and the sole of the permeable layer; the overlying rocks are deformed, and new cracks form at the boundaries of the interlayers or old ones expand.

Various liquids are used as hydraulic fracturing fluids, which can be divided into two groups according to their physico-chemical properties: hydrocarbon-

based liquids and water-based liquids. According to their purpose, liquids are divided into three categories: rupture fluid, sand carrier fluid, and sales fluid.

Hydrocarbon liquids are used in oil wells; these include high viscosity oil, fuel oil, diesel fuel or kerosene thickened with oil soaps. Aqueous solutions are used in injection wells, these include: an aqueous solution of sulfite-alcohol bard, fresh or salt water, hydrochloric and hydrofluoric acids, thickened with reagents-thickeners. Various emulsions are widely used as hydraulic fracturing fluids: oil-acid (hydrophobic), oil-water (hydrophilic) and acid-kerosene.

In addition to the general requirements, the following requirements are imposed on the sand carrier fluid: it should have a minimum filterability and a viscosity that would make it possible to keep the sand suspended. The high retention capacity of the sand carrier fluid should prevent the possibility of sand settling on

the path of the sand carrier to the face, as well as the loss of sand mobility in the crack itself.

Increasing the viscosity and reducing the filterability of liquids is achieved by introducing additives into them. Such additives for hydrocarbon liquids are salts of organic acids, high-molecular and colloidal compounds of oils.

Sales fluids are pumped into the well only in order to bring the sand carrier fluid to the bottom of the well. Thus, the volume of the sales fluid is equal to the volume of the tubing through which the sand carrier fluid is pumped. The volume of the annular space between the tubing shoe and the upper filter holes is added to the calculated tubing volume. The sales fluid under all conditions must have a minimum viscosity in order to reduce pressure losses during pumping. Almost any inexpensive liquid available in sufficient quantities, and most often ordinary water, is used as a selling liquid.

The filler is used to fill the formed cracks and prevent them from closing when pressure is removed and must meet the following requirements:

- have sufficient mechanical strength so as not to collapse in cracks under the influence of the weight of rocks;

- maintain high permeability.

These conditions are satisfied by well-rounded homogeneous quartz sand. However, the sand has a very high density, which is very different from the density of the liquid, which contributes to its subsidence from the liquid flow and makes it difficult to fill cracks. In this regard, glass balls, as well as bauxite grains of the appropriate size and ground walnut shells have recently been used in world practice as a filler. Fillers made of particularly strong artificial synthetic polymer substances with a density close to the density of the sand carrier liquid are used.

The following wells are selected for hydraulic fracturing:

- with low productivity;
- with high reservoir pressure, but with low reservoir permeability;
- with a polluted bottom-hole zone;
- with a high gas factor;
- injection pumps with low pick-up;
- injection pumps to extend the absorption interval.

Before starting work, the bottom of the well should be cleaned best by flushing. In some cases, to improve the filtration properties of layers, it is recommended to carry out hydrochloric acid or mud treatment and additional perforation. These measures reduce the pressure of the rupture and increase its effectiveness. The best effect is provided by hydroblasting perforation of the interval intended for rupture.

After cleaning, pumping and compressor pipes are lowered into the well in order to have less pressure loss when selling. To protect the casing from the effects of high pressure, a packer is sometimes installed over the ruptured formation. At high pressures during hydraulic fracturing, very large forces act on the packer from below. To prevent the packer from shifting along the column, a hydraulic anchor is installed on the pipes above the packer.

After lowering the pipes with a packer and an anchor, a head is installed at the wellhead, to which pumping units are connected for injection.

Initially, the rupture fluid is pumped by pumping units. As the pump is pumped, the pressure gradually increases. At the moment when the pressure at the bottom reaches a certain value, the formation will break and a crack will form. The moment of rupture is detected by a sharp drop in pressure on the pressure gauge installed on the switch line. After the rupture, the pressure at the mouth drops, and the flow rate of the injected liquid increases greatly – the crack begins to work and the well begins to take more liquids than it took before the rupture.

After the formation rupture, they proceed to pumping the sand carrier fluid. The greatest effect is achieved when pumping the sand carrier fluid at high speeds and at high injection pressures.

Then the liquid with sand is forced into the formation by pumping the sales fluid at maximum pressure and at maximum speed to ensure the fastest filling of cracks with sand. To do this, connect the largest number of pumping units. The amount of sales fluid must be equal to the capacity of the pipe column. When pumping an excessive amount of sales fluid, it can push the sand into the depth of the formation and after pressure is removed, the crack in the immediate vicinity of the well face may close, then the effect of the rupture can be reduced to zero.

As a sales fluid, oil is used for oil and water for injection. After the sale, the mouth is closed and the well is left alone until the pressure at the mouth drops to zero. Then the well is washed, cleaned of sand, and the development begins.

Calculations. For hydraulic fracturing, a set of equipment is used, which includes: pumping units, sand mixing machines, tankers for transporting rupture fluids, wellhead fittings, packers, anchors and other auxiliary equipment. The main equipment is pumping units. They are mounted on the chassis of three-axle heavy trucks with a load capacity of 10-12 tons. An example is given for calculations based on well data. Data on the well: depth $H = 2000$ m; diameter of the production column $D = 16.8$ cm; effective reservoir capacity $h = 10$ m; the perforation interval of the production column is 1980 – 1990 m; the number of holes 1 m of the effective reservoir capacity is 10; the well productivity coefficient $K = 0.115$ tons /day, atm. reservoir pressure $R_{pl} = 150$ atm; $R_{zab.} = 120$ atm; there is no water and sand in the production of the well; the method of operation is deep-pumping. The oil reservoir is composed of fine-grained sandstone (cemented); average porosity is 0.21; permeability is 50 md, oil saturation is 70%; there is natural fracturing; the reservoir regime is elastic-water.

According to experimental data, the volume of the rupture fluid ranges from 5-10 m³.

For this well, we accept $V_p = 7.5$ m³ of oil. It is recommended to take the following concentration of sand: for oil with a viscosity of more than 50 spz 150 – 300 g / l, and for thickened oils with a viscosity of up to 250 spz 300 – 500 g / l.

We accept $C = 300$ g/l or 0.3 g/m³.

Then the volume of the sand carrier fluid

$$V_{\text{сцен}} = \frac{G_n}{C} = \frac{8}{0,3} = 26,7 \text{ m}^3$$

G_n – the weight of sand in tons (according to experimental data, 8-10 tons of sand are usually pumped).

Conclusions. Thus, in case of hydraulic rupture, the following tasks should be solved [3]:

- 1) creating a crack
- 2) keeping the crack open
- 3) tear fluid removal
- 4) increase of reservoir productivity.

The hydraulic fracturing method has many technological solutions due to the characteristics of a particular processing object (oil, gas or injection well) and the achieved goal [4].

Hydraulic fracturing technologies differ, first of all, in the volume of injection of process fluids and wedging materials and, accordingly, in the size of cracks. With local fracturing, the length of the cracks formed is 10-20 m, with fracturing with the formation of extended cracks, the optimal length of the fixed crack is usually 40-60 m; with deep-penetrating hydraulic fracturing 80 – 120 m, and with massive fracturing – 1000 m or more [4].

When designing hydraulic fracturing, the following steps must be performed:

1. Selection of wells for processing, taking into account the existing or projected development system, ensuring maximum oil and gas production at a minimum cost.

2. Determination of the optimal crack geometry - length and conductivity, taking into account the permeability of the formation, the well placement system, the distance of the well from gas or oil-water contact.

3. Selection of a crack propagation model based on the analysis of the mechanical properties of the rock, stress distribution in the formation and preliminary experiments.

References

1. Jekonomides M., Olini R., Val'ko P. Unificirovannyj dizajn gidrorazryva plasta. Ot teorii k praktike M.: Izd-vo Institut komp'juternyh issledovaniy, 2007. 236 s. [in Russian].
2. GOST 39-195-86. Neft'. Metod opredelenija kojefficienta vytesnenija nefti vodoj v laboratornyh uslovijah. M.: Iz-voMinneftprom, 1986. C. 19.[in Russian].
3. Ocenka vlijanija tehnologii GRP na vyrabotku zapasov nefti uchastka zalezhi / I.V. Vladimirov [i dr.] // Neftepromyslovoe delo. 2012. No 1. S. 60-61. [in Russian].
4. Cutler R.A., Enniss D.O., Jones A. H., Swanson S.R. Fracture Conductivity Comparison of Ceramic Proppants// Society of Petroleum Engineers Journal: электрон. науч. журн. 1985. No2. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2118/11634-PA>